

PHYSICAL APPEARANCE SHORES UP JOB PERFORMANCE: A DEEPER LOOK ON WHITE-COLLAR GEN Z LABOR FORCE IN EMERGING MARKETS

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INTRODUCTION

Born between 1997 and 2012, Gen Z—also known as "Zoomers," "Netizens," "Children of the Internet," "Digital Generation," and "Digital Natives" (Levick-aite, 2010)—make up a sizable section of the labour force these days.

Gen Z demonstrate themselves as Open-Mindedness, Sense of Adventures, Eagerness, Determination, Drive and Competition ((Seemiller et al., 2019). Meanwhile, experts highlight Zers with a variety of characteristics, including the desire to advance quickly and health consciousness (Dwivedula et al., 2019).

The requirement for physically fit staff in the hospitality business, particularly the hotel sector, appears to be a strain on employees (Tsaur & Tang, 2013). And Gen Z—an important segment of the hotel workforce—is also feeling the pinch.

Working in the framework of the requirement for physical appearance as well as fast-achievement ambition, Gen Z in the hotel industry is eager for big outcomes. Their efforts are evident in their job performance. The goal of this study is to mould their desire in a healthy and effective way.

PURPOSE

Reaching job performance goals is a must for any employee, especially Generation Z, who has a strong desire for quick success. Outlining the road to job performance appears to be highly worthwhile.

Described from Ken Blanchard's PEFROM Model, the interaction of individuals within a team is particularly important—it is solid platform to transfer team support into the planned results. And a team is made up of people who have collected

around a person who has a nice physical look, which is visually reflected by the individual's body fitness, as evaluated by the Body Mass Index (BMI). The combination of (a) the research of Dickey-Bryant and his colleagues (1986) concluded that "physical attractiveness may well be a determinant of occupational success" and (b) the phenomenon of Gen Z "taking care of well-beings"—both mental health and physical appearance (Dolot, 2018) can expose the thread between physical appearance, team collaboration, career ambition, and job performance.

Conclusively, it should be conducted a closer examination of:

- (1) physical appearance and relationship to form a team or cohort or alliance; and
- (2) team or cohort or alliance to create collaboration; and
- (3) job performance with the assistance from the team and individual's strong ambition to achieve personal job targets.

PROBLEM

In Vietnam, the tourism industry provides 9.2% of GDP, and the government expects it to contribute 17% by 2030. And the demand for new labour is expected to be over 100,000 people by the end of 2030 as a report of Vietnam Travel Department in 2022. The possibilities for Gen Z in this sector are enormous. Consequently, the demand of smart approaches to "be successful in my career" appears to be a large calling.

The goal of this research is to carve a route for such persons by answering the research question: *In what ways can physical appearance influence job performance?*

There has been no research to date into the relationship between physical attractiveness and job performance in the Vietnam hotel industry. It is one of the primary reasons for carrying out this study.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RESEARCH

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

LOGIC OF THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Gen Z takes care of their physical appearance (as evidenced by a quantitative parameter such as BMI), and they can attract people to form a team or alliance (based on the Theory of Attraction). Working in a team, that individual pays and receives team collaboration, which creates ideal conditions for that individual to complete his or her obligations and duties.

Career ambition, a major feature of Generation Z, will have an impact on the progress between task fulfillment and job performance (according to the Theory of Expectancy-Value).

CONSTRUCTS

Physical Appearance in Workplace - Gen Z of Hotel Sector

For decades, physical appearance has been one of the unresolved topics, partially owing to its intriguing features and partly due to diverse cultural or perceptive perspectives. One widely held belief is that physical beauty is more important for women than for males. However, studies have shown that physical attractiveness is just as essential for males as it is for women (Harper, 2000).

Physical attractiveness is positively connected with physical strength, with more attractive people seen as stronger (Eagly et al., 1991). Furthermore, Mobius and Rosenblat (2006) concluded that attractive persons are perceived to be more capable., conditional on productive talents, which means they are seen as capable of executing activities at a greater level than less attractive persons.

From social aspects, persons who are physically appealing are typically seen as more friendly, dominant, sexually warm, mentally healthy, clever, and socially skillful (Feingold, 1992). These characteristics are frequently correlated with success in a variety of domains, including occupational success; it may be a determinant of occupational success, emphasizing the relevance of looks in the workplace (Dickey-Bryant et al., 1986b).

Physical attractiveness has been demonstrated to influence productivity in addition to its impact on professional performance (Becker & Geer, 1957) (Sørensen & Sonne-Holm, 1985). Physical attractiveness is an important factor in how people are seen on the job, with more attractive people often being given greater opportunities and advantages. This can lead to improved levels of job satisfaction and motivation, resulting in enhanced productivity.

Physical appearance is important in the hotel sector for making a good first impression on customers. Hotel workers are responsible for projecting a professional image and giving customers with a memorable experience as the establishment's face.

Physical attractiveness is tough to assess. Body fitness is commonly acknowledged as one of the physical appearance metrics. BMI (Body Mass Index) is the most obvious indicator of physical fitness.

BMI is typically derived from WHO definitions, such as BMI ranging from 18.50 to 24.90 indicating "good body shape" or "good physical health." However, according to the Diabetes Association of Asia (IDI & WPRO), the BMI of Vietnamese persons in "good body shape" or "good physical health" ranges from 18.50 to 22.90, based on the ASEAN framework.

And the big question, so far, is why Gen Z in hotel sector matters. According to a PricewaterhouseCoopers report from 2019, Gen Z entered the workforce of approximately 13 million people, accounting for 19% of the labor force in Vietnam. By 2025, Gen Z is expected to account for approximately 25% of the Vietnam labor force. It anticipates a 15% annual increase in the requirement for new work force in the hotel and travel industries (Vietnam National Administration of Tourism, 2019). In short, the amount of Gen Z workers entering the hotel industry is significant. According to the characteristics of Generation Z, the need to "be successful at work" is evident.

Team or Group Collaboration

Today's fast-paced commercial climate, collaboration at work has become an increasingly popular work style. Employees collaborate to achieve a common purpose that benefits both the organization and its employees (Adler & Heckscher, 2018). Collaboration promotes both individual and societal growth, as well as collaborative understanding and knowledge.

Trust is a critical component of workplace collaboration (Sloan & Oliver, 2013). Employees that lack trust are less likely to share information, take risks, and collaborate efficiently. To build trust, open conversation, active listening, and a willingness to be vulnerable with one another are required.

A healthy networking culture is also crucial to Collaboration at Work. It helps to promote information sharing, cooperation, and problem-solving. Employees who are well-connected within their organizations and industries are more likely to collaborate effectively and achieve better outcomes.

Collaboration at Work requires a good networking culture. It promotes accountability (Fuller & Marler, 2009), problem resolution (Plomp et al., 2016), and teamwork (Sloan & Oliver, 2013). Employees that are well-connected inside their organizations and sectors are more likely to collaborate successfully and generate greater results (Morrison & Phelps, 1999).

More formalized collaborative practices can include collaborative peer groups and critical friendships. These practices allow employees to work together in structured groups, sharing ideas, and feedback to achieve common goals. Collaboration peer groups and critical friendships are examples of more organized collaborative approaches. These techniques enable employees to collaborate in structured groups, sharing ideas and feedback in order to achieve common goals (Farrell et al., 2001).

Career Ambition at Work

Motivation is an important part of human behavior (Eccles & Wigfield, 2001; Fera Tracy et al., 2015), and classify human behavior motives into three categories: getting ahead, getting along, and making sense of it all.

Career Movement is one way people try to go ahead. Career movement is described as horizontal trans-grading within an organization (Hoekstra, 2011). It entails transferring from one position to another within the same organization rather than migrating to a new organization.

Career Ambition is another important aspect of motivation and is derived from the five purposes of work. These include need fulfilment (Maslow), public identity (Lent & Brown, self-concept (Super), group identity (Lent & Brown), and existential meaning (Csikszentmihalyi).

Career ambition is frequently associated with the interests of Realistic, Investigative, Artistic, Social, Enterprising, or Conventional types, sometimes known as RIASEC.

Career ambition is regarded as a crucial aspect in professional growth by the Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT). SCCT, according to Robert W. Lent (1994), and Tam et al. (2008), highlights the role of individual interests, aspirations, and self-efficacy beliefs in career development.

Career ambition has also been linked to higher work performance and job happiness. According to (Huang et al., 2014), career ambition is associated to job performance and career advancement. Meanwhile, Judge & Kammeyer-Mueller (2012) discovered that individuals with high levels of career ambition had higher levels of job satisfaction and career success.

Job Performance

Job performance is an important determinant of employee success and contributes to organizational goals. It refers to the activities, behaviors, and outcomes that workers engage in or bring about that are in line with the organization's goals (Viswesvaran & Ones, 2000). Understanding job performance characteristics is critical for individuals and organizations to achieve their goals and objectives.

Job performance characteristics are divided into three categories: task performance, counterproductive conduct, and organizational citizenship behavior.

- Task performance refers to an employee's ability to carry out their job tasks efficiently and successfully. This comprises understanding about their work, technological expertise, and the capacity to perform tasks within the time span set (Harter et al., 2002; Borman & Motowidlo, 1997).
- Counterproductive behavior, on the other hand, refers to undesirable behavior or acts that are destructive to the organization. This involves absenteeism, tardiness, and engaging in unethical or unlawful activity (Sacken & Wanek, 1996)
- Organizational citizenship conduct refers to an employee's positive behavior that extends beyond their job description and adds to the organization's well-being (Hollinger & Clark, 1983; Smith et al., 1983; Brief & Motowidlo, 1986).

Job satisfaction is linked to job performance, which influences employee turnover and retention rates (Judge et al., 2001). Employees that do well on the job are more content with their jobs, which translates into greater levels of job dedication and engagement.

Furthermore, engagement is a driving factor in the relationship between job performance and career advancement (Rich et al., 2010). Employees that are engaged in their work tend to perform better, which leads to more career chances and progress.

Job satisfaction and job performance are inextricably intertwined, with each impacting the other (Judge et al, 2001). Employees feel a sense of success and pride in their work when they do well on the job, which leads to enhanced job satisfaction. Employees that are happy with their jobs are more motivated and engaged, which leads to better job performance. This positive reinforcement cycle can lead to better production, improved job morale, and overall success for both the employee and the organization.

It is impossible to overestimate the significance of job performance. Positive job performance increases motivation and helps individuals to stay on track with their careers (Jalagat, 2016). It helps people to pursue their personal and professional goals while also contributing to the organization's success. Poor job performance, on the other hand, can lead to discontent, low morale, and decreased productivity.

PROPOSITIONS

Proposition 1: Physical appearance is a glue point to form a team or cohort or alliance. It is confirmed in Theory of Attraction.

Male and female physical attractiveness is equally significant. This comment clearly confirms Harper (2000)'s thesis regarding the importance of physical beauty in society for both genders. The first advantage of physical appearance is clearly stated; physical attractiveness can provide the possessor with a sense of self-confidence.

A good-looking physical appearance or good body fitness act as a "magnet." The attraction has three levels:

- The first level is the physical appearance itself—as Alan Feingold pointed out in 1992, those with good body form were viewed as more friendly, dominant, sexually warm, mentally healthy, intellectual, and socially skilful.
- The second level is "forming a team or cohort" at work—as a result of level 1, the owner of a good-looking physical appearance might attract others in the company, both from the same working function and from different working functions. From there, an official or unofficial cohort or team can be formed.
- The third level is teamwork, which is an irresistible result of working in a group or cohort. It is the primary root of demonstrating teamwork.

In summary, physical appearance implies a very appealing "gravity" to attract the attention of others and then to establish integration in tasking.

Proposition 2: Collaboration enables to fulfil tasks at work.

The foundation of a team's collaboration was identified. It is a human relationship; without it, all tasks of a team, and of course of an individual, can run in a "mechanical process." Human relationships require a healthy working environment to allow collaboration in the sense of sustainability.

Collaboration within a team or group can improve personal job performance from two perspectives: team and individual. Again, constructive behaviours were encouraged to connect daily task completion to individual's work performance. It signifies that an individual's KPIs could not be met without the help of a team or cohort, as demonstrated by the team's or cohort's daily constructive activities. Specifically, no matter how excellent team collaboration was, a person's job performance just stopped at a bad level unless that person obsesses a very high willingness to attain aims.

The positive team behaviours were emphasized and must be carried out to meet targets, objectives, or KPIs, while also completing each individual's task. The disadvantage of cooperation is that if the targets or objectives are not well stated, the strengths of collaboration may turn to become a very weak conveyor leading to the wrong "destination."

Proposition 3: Career ambition serves as an external enabler in the process of completing a task or achieving a goal. It is described from Theory of Expectancy-Value.

Working with the Expectancy-Value theory, an individual who is fully engaged in his effort to accomplish a specifically defined objective can demonstrate his ambition at work.

Most people have ambition, whether it is high, middle, or low. That fact is "an employee's mate." The "desire to move up" should be strongly valued and promoted. Career aspiration is frequently likened to "adrenaline to blood" or "gasoline to locomotive." All remarks might be construed to indicate that professional desire is deserving of serious consideration as an important component in the working environment.

The very important factor to transform aspiration into job performance was portrayed in a sketch with bold and strong lines to demonstrate career ambition and circumstances to turn it into personal job performance: capacity. That includes the individual's knowledge, skills, and experience; without the ability to translate ambition into results, even very high-level ambition will fail to convey results as good job performance.

And it is a wonderful announcement about the strain that results from having very high ambition at work, which continues to contribute to the character of employees' ambition. The pressure might be applied to the person with the aspiration as well as his or her peers in the group or cohort. And the notice went even further when a warning was issued—harmful to team collaboration and the destruction of trust and relationships. It appears to be an important support for the thesis that "too good is not good."

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

The MIX approach is utilized to address the research question.

The research will be carried out in a local business group comprised of four company units: Welding Unit (production), MDF (middle density fiberwood) Unit (manufacturing), Trading and Service Unit, and Hospitality Unit.

Distributed throughout Vietnam, from North to South, five hotels (3-star and 4-star) and two resorts (4-star) of the Hospitality Unit are the target of this research.

Before conducting the data collection and interview, the researcher will:

- get permission from top management board (Group President and Hospitality Unit Head); and
- sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement with each hotel or resort; and

- go over the plan with the Human Resources Department of each hotel or resort; and
 - prepare all facilities and train each hotel or resort's Human Resource Department on data collection and processing; and
 - support and co-explain the goal of the research and the data gathering process to all hotel or resort personnel.
- a. Quantitative Research:
- Around 300 data of white-collar Gen Z employees including staffs and middle managers will be collected.
 - The collection of demographic data:
 - o The data will be anonymous.
 - o Only 6 inputs will be collected: gender, year of birth, height (cm), weight (kg), number of months or years worked at the current hotel or resort, and number of positions promoted during that time.
 - o Human Resource Department of each hotel or resort will be in charge of collecting demographic data with the support from researcher.
 - o The data will be delivered by research-join-accepting correspondents to the receiving center via the Zalo chat feature using the formula shown in the example “Male – 1998 – 178 – 70 – 42 – 3”. It can be read that the person is Male, born in 1998, 178cm tall, 70kg heavy, has worked for the current organization for 42 months, and has been promoted 3 times.
 - o All corresponded data will be collected, then verified if needed.
 - The collection of job correspondent’s job performance
 - o Human Resource Department will provide data on yearly job performance appraisals for each appropriate correspondent.
 - Duration estimate: 4 weeks.
- b. Qualitative Research:
- o 16 face-to-face interviews will be done with 8 middle-managers (at least 1 manager from 1 hotel/resort) and 8 employees (at least 1 employee from 1 hotel/resort).
 - o The interviews aim to find out:
 - physical appearance is a glue point to form a team or cohort or alliance;
 - team or cohort demonstrates collaboration, which enables individual tasks;
 - career ambition serves as an external enabler in the process of completing a task or achieving a goal;
 - high personal job performance is built by the collaboration of others and the individual's strong professional drive.
 - o Duration estimated: 04 weeks
 - o Tentative plan of qualitative interview:

- i. As a foundation for the deductive technique, 4 topics will be discovered as early as the first step of the interview process. The research will not draw out any categories or sub-categories with the objective that the subject would freely uncover them throughout the interview—without any preset thought frame. The research can benefit from subjective contributions and concepts provided by interviewees.
 Theme 1—The effects of physical appearance.
 Theme 2—Collaboration enabling to fulfil tasks at work.
 Theme 3—Career ambition gearing task fulfilment to reach job performance.
 Theme 4—High personal job performance lifting to higher career stage.
- ii. The semi-structured interview method was employed to collect data for the study. All questions were written in the structure of a deductive approach based on the themes.
- iii. Questions of interview are listed below:

Themes Guide	General Questions	Exploring Questions
1. The effects of physical appearance (PA)	What are the links between PA and job performance?	What are the benefits of PA for the “owner”? What are the effects of PA to working group or cohort?
2. Team or cohort demonstrates collaboration, which enables individual tasks	How does collaboration from group or cohort contribute to individual’s task?	What is the pedestal of collaboration in working environment? What are the grey points of collaboration? What is the conditions to enhance collaboration from cohort onto the task fulfilment of an individual?
3. Career ambition gearing task fulfilment to reach job performance	What do you think about career ambition?	Any challenges to deal if a person hold a very high ambition at work? How can you define a level of career ambition? Aside of career ambition, which factor can be critical to bring ambition into job performance?

4. High personal job performance (JP) lifting to higher career stage	What are the main challenges of personal career success?	In your opinion, between collaboration for group or cohort and career ambition, which one is playing more crucial to JP? Is there any recommendation or remark about JP in work?
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ORIGINALITY/VALUE

The research is limited to the hotel labour force in Vietnam. it also focuses on Gen Z. Practical implications for Gen Z at work: try to achieve or maintain well-being (both mentally and physically), then build and improve relationships with others to gain collaboration, so that daily tasks can be completed efficiently and effectively; then, being amplified with high career ambition, their job performance can be fulfilled to align with their career path.

Managerial implications: recognizing the undeniable fact that physical attractiveness can positively affect their employees' job performance, managers can promote well-being in their working circle (i.e. encourage physical activities such as gym, physical exercise, yoga, etc., which are now promoted in many firms).

FINDINGS/DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

So far, no data has been collected, and no interviews have been conducted. As a result, no specific results for discussion and conclusion are generated at this point in time.

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